

Methods for: "Weaker selection on genes with treatment-specific expression consistent with a limit on plasticity evolution in *Arabidopsis thaliana*"

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1 Materials and methods

1.1 RNA-seq run annotation

We amassed an initial set of RNA-seq runs from the SUSTech Arabidopsis RNA-seq database V2 (Zhang et al., 2020) (<http://ipf.sustech.edu.cn/pub/athrdb/>) excluding any samples not associated with a publication or lacking a tissue type label. On May 24th, 2022 we also downloaded all run metadata from the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) returned by the following search term: ("Arabidopsis thaliana"[Organism] AND "RNA"[Source]) OR ("Arabidopsis thaliana"[Organism] AND "RNA-Seq"[Strategy]) OR ("Arabidopsis thaliana"[Organism] AND "TRANSCRIPTOMIC"[Source]). All SRA runs were linked to their associated publications, if possible, using Entrez. Any SRA run numbers that we could not link to a PUBMED ID or DOI were omitted. We then manually removed all SRA runs that originated from transgenic, mutant, hybrid, grafted, cell culture, polyploid, or aneuploid samples based on information in the SRA metadata and associated publications. Runs from any naturally-occurring *A. thaliana* accession were included. We also omitted SRA runs that focused on sequencing non-coding RNA (ncRNA-seq, miRNA-seq, lncRNA-seq, sRNA-seq, etc.). After applying these criteria, any bioprojects with 8 or fewer SRA run numbers remaining were also omitted.

All runs were labeled with treatment and tissue type descriptions using the Plant Experimental Conditions Ontology (PECO) and the Plant Ontology (PO) (Cooper et al., 2018), respectively, based on information in their associated publications and SRA metadata. In our analysis, control exposure was defined as long day conditions (12 hrs light exposure or longer, but not constant light) and growing temperatures in the range of 18° - 26°, inclusive, without explicit application of stress or nutrient limitation. Warm treatments were defined as 27° or higher, while cold treatments were defined as 17° or lower. Any studies

that did not report both day length and growing temperature were omitted. Any runs that could not be linked to treatments based on their annotations in the SRA or Sustech databases were also omitted. Treatment with polyethylene glycol (PEG) was categorized as drought exposure. Samples from plants that were recovering from stress were categorized according to the growth conditions of the recovery state instead of the stressed state. When appropriate, we labeled samples with multiple PECO terms. For example, a sample that was subjected to both heat stress and high light stress would get two PECO terms (one for each stress) and be treated separately from samples subjected to only heat stress or only light stress. Tissue type labels were eventually collapsed to the following categories: whole plant, shoot, root, leaf, seed, and a combined category of flower and fruit tissues. The flower and fruit tissue categories were combined because of their developmental relationship and small size relative to the other categories. In the end, we had a dataset of 24,101 sequencing runs from 306 published studies.

1.2 RNA-seq run processing

All RNA-seq runs were processed using the same workflow to remove the effects of bioinformatic processing differences between studies on expression level. First, runs were downloaded using the SRA toolkit (v2.10.7), but 90 runs were not publicly available and thus failed to download. All successfully downloaded runs were trimmed using fastp v0.23.1 (Chen et al., 2018), requiring a minimum quality score of 20 and a minimum read length of at least 25 bp (-q 20 -l 25). Trimming results were compiled using multiqc v1.7 (Ewels et al., 2016). All trimmed runs were then aligned to a decoy-aware transcriptome index made by combining the primary transcripts of the Araport11 genome annotation (Cheng et al., 2017) with the *A. thaliana* genome in salmon v1.2.1 (Patro et al., 2017) using an index size of 25bp. The salmon outputs of each run were then combined with a custom R script to create an gene-by-run expression matrix. We omitted 423 runs with a mapping rate < 1 %, 215 runs with zero mapped transcripts, and 18 genes with zero mapped transcripts across all runs from further analysis. We note that although this cut-off does not exclude samples with more modest mapping rates (e.g. 20 - 60 %) the choice to include these samples was to avoid removing large chunks of data as "outliers" and analyzing only those samples that conform to our expectations.

1.3 Whole genome sequence data processing

We downloaded whole genome sequencing data for 1135 *A. thaliana* accessions from the 1001 genomes project panel (SRA project SRP056687) (Alonso-Blanco et al., 2016) using the SRA toolkit. All runs were trimmed using fastp (Chen et al., 2018), requiring a minimum quality score of 20 and a read length of at least 30 bp (-q 20 -l 30). Trimmed reads were then aligned to the *A. thaliana* reference genome using BWA v0.7.17 (Li and Durbin, 2009). The alignments were sorted and converted to BAM format with SAMTOOLS v1.11 (Danecek et al.,

2021), then optical duplicates were marked with picardtools v2.22.1. Haplotypes were called for each accession, then combined and jointly genotyped with GATK v4.1.4.1 assuming a sample ploidy of 2, heterozygosity of 0.001, indel-heterozygosity of 0.001, and minimum base quality score of 20. Invariant sites were included in the genotype calls with the `-include-non-variant-sites` option. All calls were restricted to only coding sequence (CDS) regions based on the Araport11 annotation by supplying a BED file of CDS coordinates made with bedtools (v2.29.2). Following Korunes and Samuk (2021), variant and invariant sites were filtered separately using both GATK and vcftools v0.1.15 (Danecek et al., 2011). Variant sites were filtered if they met any of the following criteria: $QD < 2$, $QUAL < 30$, $MQ < 40$, $FS > 60$, $HaplotypeScore > 13$, $MQRankSum < -12.5$, $ReadPosRankSum < -8.0$, mean depth < 10 , mean depth > 75 , missing genotype calls $> 20\%$, being an indel, or having more than 2 alleles. In the end, 1,915,859 variant sites across all coding sequences were retained for further analysis. Invariant sites were filtered if they met any of the following criteria: $QUAL > 100$, mean depth < 10 , mean depth > 75 , missing genotype calls $> 20\%$. Finally, variant sites were annotated using snpEff (Java v15.0.2) (Cingolani et al., 2012b) and variants labeled as either missense or synonymous were separated into different files using SnpSift (Cingolani et al., 2012a).

1.4 Selection estimated from between-species divergence

We identified 1:1 orthologs between the primary transcripts of *A. thaliana* and *Arabidopsis lyrata* with Orthofinder v2.5.4 (Emms and Kelly, 2019). For each 1:1 ortholog, we aligned their protein sequences with MAFFT L-INS-I v7.475 (Katoh and Standley, 2013), then converted the protein alignments to gapless codon-based alignments using pal2nal v14 (Suyama et al., 2006). Using the gapless codon-based alignments, we estimated dN/dS using the Nei and Gojobori (1986) method implemented as a custom Biopython v1.79 script and implemented through the codeml program in the PAML package v4.9 (Yang, 2007). Unlike codeml, the custom Biopython script also returns counts of nonsynonymous (N) and synonymous sites (S) within each gene as described in Nei and Gojobori (1986), which we later used to calculate nucleotide diversity per nonsynonymous site (π_N) and per synonymous site (π_S). Before proceeding with more analyses, we confirmed that our estimates of dN and dS were consistent between our Biopython script and codeml (Pearson correlations $dN : \rho = 0.9998$, $dS : \rho = 0.9809$). The outputs of the Biopython script were used in all subsequent analyses.

1.5 Selection estimated from within-species polymorphism

1.5.1 Nucleotide diversity at nonsynonymous sites.

Nucleotide diversity (π) was calculated for each gene with pixy v1.2.3.beta1 (Korunes and Samuk, 2021) three times: once using all sites (both variant and invariant), once using missense sites plus invariant sites, and once using

synonymous sites plus invariant sites. These estimates were then converted to π , π_N , and π_S , respectively, by first multiplying the per site estimate output from pixy by the number of sites included in the analysis. Then, to get π_N and π_S , the values from analyses of missense plus invariant, and synonymous plus invariant sites were divided by the N and S values for each gene, respectively, as determined by the method in Nei and Gojobori (1986).

1.5.2 Tajima's D.

We next calculated Tajima's D for each gene. First, we calculated π and Watterson's Theta (θ_W) for each variant site i within a gene (π_i and θ_{W_i} respectively). In this case, π_i was calculated as:

$$\pi_i = \left(\frac{n_i}{n_i - 1} \right) \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^2 p_{ij}^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

Where n_i is the number of sequenced chromosomes with non-missing genotypes for variant i , p_{i1} is the frequency of the reference allele, and p_{i2} is the frequency of the alternative allele. Then, θ_{W_i} was calculated as:

$$\theta_{W_i} = \frac{1}{a_i} \quad (2)$$

Where a_i is:

$$a_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i-1} \frac{1}{j} \quad (3)$$

This calculation of θ_{W_i} is equivalent to the usual calculation of θ_W with the number of segregating sites set to one. Next, the variance in Tajima's D was calculated for each site as:

$$Var(\pi_i - \theta_{W_i}) = \frac{\frac{n_i+1}{3(n_i-1)} - \frac{1}{a_i}}{a_i} \quad (4)$$

This is equivalent to equation 38 in Tajima (1989) with the number of segregating sites set to one.

Finally, the results of the above calculations were combined in the following formula:

$$D_i = \frac{\pi_i - \theta_{W_i}}{\sqrt{Var(\pi_i - \theta_{W_i})}} \quad (5)$$

To get Tajima's D for each gene, we then averaged across the D_i values for all the variant sites within a gene.

1.5.3 Direction of Selection (DoS).

Counts of nonsynonymous and synonymous polymorphisms within each gene (P_N and P_S , respectively) were determined with bedtools (v2.29.2). The number of nonsynonymous and synonymous differences (D_N and D_S , respectively)

between *A. thaliana* genes and their 1:1 *A. lyrata* orthologs, if present, were estimated during the process of calculating dN/dS in Biopython as described above. These values were then used to calculate the direction of selection (DoS) (Stoletzki and Eyre-Walker, 2011) as follows:

$$DoS = \frac{D_N}{D_N + D_S} - \frac{P_N}{P_N + P_S} \quad (6)$$

We chose this metric, as opposed to the proportion of amino acid substitutions driven by positive selection (α), because it is less biased than α (Stoletzki and Eyre-Walker, 2011) and was successfully used in studies similar to ours (Paape et al., 2013). Furthermore, we found that α often returns uninterpretable negative values when applied to *A. thaliana*, perhaps because of an excess of slightly deleterious polymorphisms (Nordborg et al., 2005) due to their predominantly selfing mating system (Charlesworth, 1994).

1.6 Treatment specificity

Treatment specificity (τ) was estimated separately for runs from each tissue type using the following formula (Yanai et al., 2005):

$$\tau = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N 1 - \frac{x_i}{\max x}}{N - 1} \quad (7)$$

Where x is the vector of average expression values of a gene in each treatment category, measured in transcripts per million (TPM), and where N is the number of treatment categories. Dividing by N means that τ varies between zero and one, where zero indicates no specificity and one indicates exclusive specificity to a single treatment. We used this metric of specificity because it is consistently more robust than others (Kryuchkova-Mostacci and Robinson-Rechavi, 2017) and is normalized by the number of treatments included, making it comparable across data sets. We also applied the same formula to calculate tissue specificity in several different treatment conditions.

1.7 Simulating correlations between average expression and specificity index

Average expression level and measures of expression specificity are correlated by definition because genes with more treatment/tissue-specific expression will have lower average expression across all treatment/tissue categories. We ran two simulations to better illustrate the factors driving the correlation between average expression and the specificity index, τ . In both simulations, we generated 1000 random matrices, where each element x_{ij} represented the expression of gene i in experiment j , by sampling from a zero-inflated negative binomial distribution:

$$x_{ij} \sim ZINegBinom(N, p_1, p_2) \quad (8)$$

Where the size and probability parameters of the negative binomial component were $N = 100$ and $p_1 = 0.1$, respectively, while the probability of an expression value being non-zero was $p_2 = 0.4$. All matrices included 5 groups of columns, with 5 columns per group, representing replicates of tissue/treatment groups. For both simulations, we averaged across columns within each group to simulate the calculation of tissue/treatment-wide averages. We then applied the formula for τ across the rows of this averaged matrix to get expression specificity. In one simulation, we calculated expression level by averaging across the rows of the expression matrix. In a second simulation, we excluded experiments where a gene was not expressed ($x_{ij} = 0$) from the calculation of average expression.

1.8 Average expression, length, GC content, family size

Calculating the average expression of each gene was a three-step process. First, we averaged together runs with matching SRA experiment IDs because these runs represented technical replicates of the same biological sample and treatment conditions. Second, we partitioned our gene-by-experiment expression matrix by the tissue type each sample came from. Finally, for each tissue type’s expression matrix, we averaged across all of the expression values of each gene across all experiments, excluding values < 5 transcripts per million (TPM). We excluded values < 5 TPM from the average expression calculation to avoid a high correlation between average expression and treatment-specificity, as has been reported in previous studies (Slotte et al., 2011). This high correlation occurs because an environment-specific gene will by definition also have low average expression across environments it is rarely expressed in. Furthermore, we excluded values < 5 TPM to avoid including small expression values that could be artifacts of alignment error.

The length and GC content of each gene was measured using the bedtools nuc command (v2.29.2) and included each gene’s introns and untranslated regions when present. We included introns and untranslated regions in the estimate of gene length because they play important roles in determining rates of protein evolution (Castillo-Davis et al., 2002; Eisenberg and Levanon, 2003). Finally, the family size for each gene was estimated as the number of *A. thaliana* genes in their respective orthogroups output by OrthoFinder.

1.9 Partial correlation analysis

Not all treatment-tissue combinations were sampled in the overall RNA-seq dataset, causing confounding between the treatment and tissue labels. We resolved this in two ways. First, we subset the data to only the treatment conditions where all tissue types were represented. Second, we subset the data by tissue type and analyzed each subset separately. For each subset, we calculated partial spearman correlations between treatment specificity and our measures of selection (dN , π_N , Tajima’s D, and DoS) after accounting for average expression (excluding values TPM < 5), gene length, and GC content using the ppcor R package (Kim, 2015). For partial correlation analyses involving π_N and

Tajima’s D , we also controlled for gene family size. We did not account for gene family size in partial correlation analyses involving dN or DoS because these metrics apply to only genes with one family member in this study. When calculating partial correlations involving dN , we excluded any genes with saturating divergence ($dS > 1$). All statistical analyses and data visualizations used R v4.0.3 and used color palettes in the `scico` R package (Cramer, 2018; Pedersen and Cramer, 2022).

1.10 Surrogate variable analysis

We recalculated treatment specificity and repeated all partial correlation analyses after correcting each data subset for technical between-experiment variation (i.e. batch effects), following an approach from (Fukushima and Pollock, 2020). Batch effects include variables that influence gene expression measurements but are not of interest to this study, such as the sequencing platform and the library prep protocol used in each experiment. First, with our data already subset by tissue type, we further subset to only include treatments with RNA-seq runs from at least two studies. This minimizes confounding between-treatment variation with the technical between-experiment variation we aimed to account for. We then applied surrogate variable analysis (SVA) using the `svaseq()` function within the SVA package (Leek and Storey, 2007) to each of these subsets. Briefly, SVA models gene expression as:

$$x_{ij} = \mu_i + f(y_i) + e_{ij} \quad (9)$$

Where x_{ij} is the expression of gene i in experiment j , μ_i is the average expression of gene i across all experiments, and y_i is the value of a predictor variable of interest for gene i . Furthermore, $f(y_i)$ gives the deviation of gene i from its average expression based on the value of y_i and e_{ij} is the residual error. SVA takes this model and partitions the residual variance, e_{ij} , into:

$$x_{ij} = \mu_i + f(y_i) + \sum_{\ell=1}^L \gamma_{\ell i} g_{\ell j} + e_{ij}^* \quad (10)$$

Where $\sum_{\ell=1}^L \gamma_{\ell i} g_{\ell j}$ gives the summed effects of L unmodeled variables ($g_{\ell j}$) for each gene and e_{ij}^* gives the gene-specific noise in expression. SVA does not attempt to estimate what the unmodeled variables influencing expression are, but rather find a set of vectors (the surrogate variables) that span the same space as \mathbf{g} :

$$x_{ij} = \mu_i + f(y_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{ki} h_{kj} + e_{ij}^* \quad (11)$$

Where each \mathbf{h}_k is a surrogate variable and each λ_k gives the effects of each surrogate variable on gene expression. For our analyses, our predictor variable y_i was treatment type. To get a measure of expression where the effects of

surrogate variables are removed, we then subtracted off the effects of surrogate variables from both sides of the above equation.

$$x_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{ki} h_{kj} = \mu_i + f(y_i) + e_{ij}^* \quad (12)$$

Where $x_{ij} - \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_{ki} h_{kj}$ gives us our expression values accounting for the effects of surrogate variables. The net result here is a reduction in the amount of unexplained or seemingly stochastic variation in expression because sources of variation have been attributed to "surrogates" that span the same space as real batch variables. We also conducted principal component analysis in R before and after SVA to verify the removal of batch effects.

References

- C. Alonso-Blanco, J. Andrade, C. Becker, F. Bemm, J. Bergelson, K. M. Borgwardt, J. Cao, E. Chae, T. M. DeZwaan, W. Ding, J. R. Ecker, M. Exposito-Alonso, A. Farlow, J. Fitz, X. Gan, D. G. Grimm, A. M. Hancock, S. R. Henz, S. Holm, M. Horton, M. Jarsulic, R. A. Kerstetter, A. Korte, P. Korte, C. Lanz, C.-R. Lee, D. Meng, T. P. Michael, R. Mott, N. W. Mulyati, T. Nägele, M. Nagler, V. Nizhynska, M. Nordborg, P. Y. Novikova, F. X. Picó, A. Platzer, F. A. Rabanal, A. Rodriguez, B. A. Rowan, P. A. Salomé, K. J. Schmid, R. J. Schmitz, Seren, F. G. Sperone, M. Sudkamp, H. Svardal, M. M. Tanzer, D. Todd, S. L. Volchenboum, C. Wang, G. Wang, X. Wang, W. Weckwerth, D. Weigel, and X. Zhou. 1,135 genomes reveal the global pattern of polymorphism in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Cell*, 166(2):481–491, July 2016. ISSN 0092-8674, 1097-4172. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2016.05.063. URL [https://www.cell.com/cell/abstract/S0092-8674\(16\)30667-5](https://www.cell.com/cell/abstract/S0092-8674(16)30667-5). Publisher: Elsevier.
- C. I. Castillo-Davis, S. L. Mekhedov, D. L. Hartl, E. V. Koonin, and F. A. Kondrashov. Selection for short introns in highly expressed genes. *Nature Genetics*, 31(4):415–418, Aug. 2002. ISSN 1546-1718. doi: 10.1038/ng940. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/ng940z>. Number: 4 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- B. Charlesworth. The effect of background selection against deleterious mutations on weakly selected, linked variants. *Genetical Research*, 63(3):213–227, June 1994. doi: 10.1017/s0016672300032365.
- S. Chen, Y. Zhou, Y. Chen, and J. Gu. fastp: an ultra-fast all-in-one FASTQ preprocessor. *Bioinformatics*, 34(17):i884–i890, Sept. 2018. ISSN 1367-4803. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/bty560. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty560>.
- C.-Y. Cheng, V. Krishnakumar, A. P. Chan, F. Thibaud-Nissen, S. Schobel, and C. D. Town. Araport11: a complete reannotation of the

- Arabidopsis thaliana* reference genome. *The Plant Journal*, 89(4): 789–804, 2017. ISSN 1365-313X. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.13415>. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/tpj.13415>. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/tpj.13415>.
- P. Cingolani, V. M. Patel, M. Coon, T. Nguyen, S. J. Land, D. M. Ruden, and X. Lu. Using *Drosophila melanogaster* as a model for genotoxic chemical mutational studies with a new program, SnpSift. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 3, 2012a. doi: 10.3389/fgene.2012.00035. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3304048/>. Publisher: Frontiers Media SA.
- P. Cingolani, A. Platts, L. L. Wang, M. Coon, T. Nguyen, L. Wang, S. J. Land, X. Lu, and D. M. Ruden. A program for annotating and predicting the effects of single nucleotide polymorphisms, SnpEff. *Fly*, 6(2):80–92, Apr. 2012b. ISSN 1933-6934. doi: 10.4161/fly.19695. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3679285/>.
- L. Cooper, A. Meier, M.-A. Laporte, J. L. Elser, C. Mungall, B. T. Sinn, D. Cavaliere, S. Carbon, N. A. Dunn, B. Smith, B. Qu, J. Preece, E. Zhang, S. Todorovic, G. Gkoutos, J. H. Doonan, D. W. Stevenson, E. Arnaud, and P. Jaiswal. The Planteome database: an integrated resource for reference ontologies, plant genomics and phenomics. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 46(D1): D1168–D1180, Jan. 2018. ISSN 0305-1048. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkx1152. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkx1152>.
- F. Crameri. Geodynamic diagnostics, scientific visualisation and StagLab 3.0. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(6):2541–2562, June 2018. ISSN 1991-959X. doi: 10.5194/gmd-11-2541-2018. URL <https://gmd.copernicus.org/articles/11/2541/2018/>. Publisher: Copernicus GmbH.
- P. Danecek, A. Auton, G. Abecasis, C. A. Albers, E. Banks, M. A. DePristo, R. E. Handsaker, G. Lunter, G. T. Marth, S. T. Sherry, G. McVean, R. Durbin, and . G. P. A. Group. The variant call format and VCFtools. *Bioinformatics*, 27(15):2156–2158, Aug. 2011. ISSN 1367-4803. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btr330. URL <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/27/15/2156/402296>. Publisher: Oxford Academic.
- P. Danecek, J. K. Bonfield, J. Liddle, J. Marshall, V. Ohan, M. O. Pollard, A. Whitwham, T. Keane, S. A. McCarthy, R. M. Davies, and H. Li. Twelve years of SAMtools and BCFtools. *GigaScience*, 10(2):giab008, Feb. 2021. ISSN 2047-217X. doi: 10.1093/gigascience/giab008. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giab008>.
- E. Eisenberg and E. Y. Levanon. Human housekeeping genes are compact. *Trends in Genetics*, 19(7):362–365, July 2003. ISSN 0168-9525. doi: 10.1016/S0168-9525(03)00140-9. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168952503001409>.

- D. M. Emms and S. Kelly. OrthoFinder: phylogenetic orthology inference for comparative genomics. *Genome Biology*, 20(1):238, Nov. 2019. ISSN 1474-760X. doi: 10.1186/s13059-019-1832-y. URL <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-019-1832-y>.
- P. Ewels, M. Magnusson, S. Lundin, and M. Källér. MultiQC: summarize analysis results for multiple tools and samples in a single report. *Bioinformatics*, 32(19):3047–3048, Oct. 2016. ISSN 1367-4803. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btw354. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw354>.
- K. Fukushima and D. D. Pollock. Amalgamated cross-species transcriptomes reveal organ-specific propensity in gene expression evolution. *Nature Communications*, 11(1):4459, Sept. 2020. ISSN 2041-1723. doi: 10.1038/s41467-020-18090-8. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-18090-8>. Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- K. Katoh and D. M. Standley. MAFFT multiple sequence alignment software version 7: improvements in performance and usability. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 30(4):772–780, Apr. 2013. ISSN 0737-4038. doi: 10.1093/molbev/mst010. URL <https://academic.oup.com/mbe/article/30/4/772/1073398>. Publisher: Oxford Academic.
- S. Kim. ppcor: an R package for a fast calculation to semi-partial correlation coefficients. *Communications for statistical applications and methods*, 22(6): 665–674, Nov. 2015. ISSN 2287-7843. doi: 10.5351/CSAM.2015.22.6.665. URL <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4681537/>.
- K. L. Korunes and K. Samuk. pixy: Unbiased estimation of nucleotide diversity and divergence in the presence of missing data. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, 21(4):1359–1368, 2021. ISSN 1755-0998. doi: 10.1111/1755-0998.13326. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1755-0998.13326>. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/1755-0998.13326>.
- N. Kryuchkova-Mostacci and M. Robinson-Rechavi. A benchmark of gene expression tissue-specificity metrics. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 18(2):205–214, Mar. 2017. ISSN 1467-5463. doi: 10.1093/bib/bbw008. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/bib/bbw008>.
- J. T. Leek and J. D. Storey. Capturing heterogeneity in gene expression studies by surrogate variable analysis. *PLOS Genetics*, 3(9):e161, Sept. 2007. ISSN 1553-7404. doi: 10.1371/journal.pgen.0030161. URL <https://journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=10.1371/journal.pgen.0030161>. Publisher: Public Library of Science.
- H. Li and R. Durbin. Fast and accurate short read alignment with Burrows–Wheeler transform. *Bioinformatics*, 25(14):1754–1760, July 2009. ISSN 1367-4803. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btp324. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btp324>.

- M. Nei and T. Gojobori. Simple methods for estimating the numbers of synonymous and nonsynonymous nucleotide substitutions. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 3(5):418–426, Sept. 1986. ISSN 0737-4038. doi: 10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a040410. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a040410>.
- M. Nordborg, T. T. Hu, Y. Ishino, J. Jhaveri, C. Toomajian, H. Zheng, E. Bakker, P. Calabrese, J. Gladstone, R. Goyal, M. Jakobsson, S. Kim, Y. Morozov, B. Padhukasahasram, V. Plagnol, N. A. Rosenberg, C. Shah, J. D. Wall, J. Wang, K. Zhao, T. Kalbfleisch, V. Schulz, M. Kreitman, and J. Bergelson. The pattern of polymorphism in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *PLoS Biology*, 3(7):e196, May 2005. ISSN 1545-7885. doi: 10.1371/journal.pbio.0030196. URL <https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.0030196>. Publisher: Public Library of Science.
- T. Paape, T. Bataillon, P. Zhou, T. J. Y. Kono, R. Briskine, N. D. Young, and P. Tiffin. Selection, genome-wide fitness effects and evolutionary rates in the model legume *Medicago truncatula*. *Molecular Ecology*, 22(13):3525–3538, 2013. ISSN 1365-294X. doi: 10.1111/mec.12329. URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/mec.12329>. eprint: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/mec.12329>.
- R. Patro, G. Duggal, M. I. Love, R. A. Irizarry, and C. Kingsford. Salmon provides fast and bias-aware quantification of transcript expression. *Nature Methods*, 14(4):417–419, Apr. 2017. ISSN 1548-7105. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.4197. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/nmeth.4197>. Number: 4 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- T. L. Pedersen and F. Cramer. *scico: Colour Palettes Based on the Scientific Colour-Maps*. R, 2022. URL <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=scico>.
- T. Slotte, T. Bataillon, T. T. Hansen, K. St. Onge, S. I. Wright, and M. H. Schierup. Genomic determinants of protein evolution and polymorphism in *Arabidopsis*. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 3:1210–1219, Jan. 2011. ISSN 1759-6653. doi: 10.1093/gbe/evr094. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evr094>.
- N. Stoletzki and A. Eyre-Walker. Estimation of the neutrality index. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 28(1):63–70, Jan. 2011. ISSN 0737-4038. doi: 10.1093/molbev/msq249. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msq249>.
- M. Suyama, D. Torrents, and P. Bork. PAL2NAL: robust conversion of protein sequence alignments into the corresponding codon alignments. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 34(suppl.2):W609–W612, July 2006. ISSN 0305-1048. doi: 10.1093/nar/gkl315. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkl315>.

- F. Tajima. Statistical method for testing the neutral mutation hypothesis by DNA polymorphism. *Genetics*, 123(3):585–595, Nov. 1989. ISSN 1943-2631. doi: 10.1093/genetics/123.3.585. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/123.3.585>.
- I. Yanai, H. Benjamin, M. Shmoish, V. Chalifa-Caspi, M. Shklar, R. Ophir, A. Bar-Even, S. Horn-Saban, M. Safran, E. Domany, D. Lancet, and O. Shmueli. Genome-wide midrange transcription profiles reveal expression level relationships in human tissue specification. *Bioinformatics*, 21(5):650–659, Mar. 2005. ISSN 1367-4803. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/bti042. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bti042>.
- Z. Yang. PAML 4: Phylogenetic Analysis by Maximum Likelihood. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 24(8):1586–1591, Aug. 2007. ISSN 0737-4038. doi: 10.1093/molbev/msm088. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msm088>.
- H. Zhang, F. Zhang, Y. Yu, L. Feng, J. Jia, B. Liu, B. Li, H. Guo, and J. Zhai. A comprehensive online database for exploring 20,000 public *Arabidopsis* RNA-seq libraries. *Molecular Plant*, 13(9):1231–1233, Sept. 2020. ISSN 1674-2052. doi: 10.1016/j.molp.2020.08.001. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1674205220302574>.